

The Determination of Mode III Fracture Toughness in Thick Composite Laminates

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, we propose a method to determine the Mode III interlaminar fracture toughness of thick composite laminates. Previous finite element results show that for edge cracked composite specimen under torsion loading, the fracture behavior is dominated by Mode III. In order to simplify the calculation, an analytical series solution employing effective moduli is derived to study the fracture behavior of edge cracked multilayer laminates. This analytical tool is employed for angle ply laminates to characterize the critical strain energy release rates. Several angle-ply laminates with artificial damage located at arbitrary interfaces are tested to find the fracture toughness. Experimental results show that G_{IIIc} ranges from 460 J/m² to 825 J/m² for most cases. Test results show that this theory and experimental method can be used to find the interlaminar G_{IIIc} for angle ply composites.

INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced composite materials are widely used in all kinds of engineering structures due to their high strengths and low densities. Because of its low stiffness in transverse directions, when out of plane loading exists, separation between plies happens, i.e., delamination. Usually the delamination modes in composite laminates contain Mode I (opening), Mode II (in plane shearing) and Mode III (out of plane tearing) fractures. Therefore it is important to characterize these fracture behaviors to prevent delamination damage.

Currently, many studies address the determination of the fracture toughness of Mode I, Mode II and the mixed modes of both. There are few methods to characterize the tearing mode (Mode III) fracture toughness, for example, the split cantilever beam (SCB) method [1], and the crack rail shear (CRS) method [2]. It seemed that significant Mode II component was found in the SCB method, and the double precracks can not propagate simultaneously in the experiment for certain CRS specimens[3]. Perhaps the most feasible way to measure the Mode III fracture toughness is the edge crack torsion (ECT) method proposed by Lee[4]. However, the position of edge crack is limited to the midplane of the specimen, and the transverse shear effect was not taken into account when the laminate is thick. The main purpose of this paper is to propose an almost pure Mode III test method for edge crack located at arbitrary interface and to characterize its interlaminar fracture toughness.

It has been shown that for an isotropic cracked rectangular beam subjected to a torque loading, the fracture mode is a pure Mode III [5,6]. Although torsion test provides a solid background for Mode III fracture, there is no analytical solution for orthotropic cracked beam. An extension of Chen's [6] work is derived here to solve the case of orthotropic beams. It seems that these generalized formula can be used to solve the edge cracked torsion problems of orthotropic bars.

In this paper the concept of effective moduli [7] is applied to analyze the torsion behavior of thick laminates. A global analytical series solution with effective shear moduli is derived and its accuracy is compared with finite element method. It is seen that the fracture is dominated by Mode III, and the effective moduli can be applied for thick laminates with large crack; albeit, the contribution from Mode I and Mode II have been neglected.

From the numerical examinations, an efficient tool using series solution is proposed to characterize the fracture toughness of several angle ply systems. Different angle ply laminates with artificial damage located at interfaces are tested to find the fracture toughness. Experimental results show that G_{IIIc} ranges from 460 J/m² to 825 J/m² for most cases.

TORSION OF COMPOSITE LAMINATES

1. Effective Moduli for Thick Laminates

For thick laminate composed of repeated sublaminates, the inhomogeneity between each lamina in a subset can be smeared out, and effective moduli employed [7]. The following equations are used to calculate the effective shear moduli of $\pm\theta$ type composite laminate made of single material system [7].

$$\bar{c}_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^N v_k c_{ij}^k \quad i, j = 1, 2, 3, 6$$

$$\bar{c}_{pq} = \left[\sum_{k=1}^N v_k c_{pq}^k / \Delta_k \right] / \Delta \quad p, q = 4, 5 \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta = \left[\sum_{k=1}^N v_k c_{44}^k / \Delta_k \right] \left[\sum_{k=1}^N v_k c_{55}^k / \Delta_k \right] - \left[\sum_{k=1}^N v_k c_{45}^k / \Delta_k \right]^2$$

$$\Delta_k = c_{44}^k c_{55}^k - (c_{45}^k)^2$$

where v_k is the volume ratio of the kth lamina in the sublaminates.

2. Global Analytical Series Solution

When the effective moduli are used, the whole laminate can be treated as an orthotropic material, and a simplified solution can be derived analytically.

For an orthotropic laminate with rectangular cross section subjected to a torque T in the x-direction (see Fig.1), the governing equation is given by [8]

$$\frac{1}{G_{xz}} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial y^2} + \frac{1}{G_{xy}} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial z^2} = -2\theta \quad (2)$$

where G_{xy} and G_{xz} are the shear moduli in the xy and xz plane, respectively, θ is the twisting angle per unit length, ψ is the stress potential with

$$\sigma_{xz} = -\frac{\partial \psi}{\partial y}, \quad \sigma_{xy} = \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z} \quad (3)$$

and other $\sigma_{ij} = 0$. The torsional rigidity GJ of this laminate is shown to be [8]

$$T / \theta = GJ = G_{xy}(2b)(2h)^3 \beta \quad (4)$$

$$\beta = \frac{32\alpha^2}{\pi^4} \sum_{m=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{1}{m^4} \left(1 - 2\frac{\alpha}{m\pi} \tanh \frac{m\pi}{2\alpha}\right) \quad (5)$$

$$\alpha = \frac{2b/2h}{\sqrt{G_{xy}/G_{xz}}} \quad (6)$$

These formulas have been applied by Kurtz and Sun [9] to find the material shear moduli G_{xy} , G_{xz} and G_{yz} of thick laminates under pure torsion. They measured the torsional rigidities of two different cross-section and set up two equations to solve the unknowns G_{xy} and G_{xz} . Zero degree specimens are tested to characterize the G_{12} and G_{13} . The transverse shear modulus G_{23} is found from 90° coupons, and is about 50-60% of G_{12} or G_{13} . For rectangular cross sections with edge crack under torsion loading, the analytical series solution can be derived in a similar way as that in [6]. Consider an edge crack specimen with crack locate at arbitrary height e (or f) as shown in Fig. 2, the governing equation is the same as Eqn. (2), with boundary condition $\psi|_{\Gamma} = \text{constant}$, where Γ is the boundary of this cross section. If we let

$$\psi = G_{xy} \theta \left[-z^2 + \phi(y, z)\right] \quad (7)$$

then Eqn.(2) will take the form

$$\frac{1}{p^2} \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial y^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \phi}{\partial z^2} = 0 \quad (8)$$

with boundary condition

$$\phi|_{\Gamma} = -z^2 \quad (9)$$

where

$$p^2 = G_{xz} / G_{xy} \quad (10)$$

In Fig. 2, $2b$ is the width parallel to the crack direction, $e + f$ is the total thickness of the orthotropic bar, and a is the crack size. Following the derivation as indicated in [6], the torsional rigidity GJ of the cross section can be shown as

$$GJ = G_{xy} \left[\frac{2b}{3} (e^3 + f^3) - \frac{4c^2 p}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^3} G_n (\tanh(n\pi e / cp) + \tanh(n\pi f / ce)) \right]$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & -\frac{4f^2}{p\pi^2} \sum_{n=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^3} \left(F_n + \frac{8f^2}{n^2\pi^3} \right) (\tanh(pn\pi a / 2f) + \tanh(pn\pi c / 2f)) \\
 & - \left. \frac{4e^2}{p\pi^2} \sum_{n=1,3,5,\dots}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^3} \left(H_n + \frac{8e^2}{n^2\pi^3} \right) (\tanh(pn\pi a / 2e) + \tanh(pn\pi c / 2e)) \right] \quad (11)
 \end{aligned}$$

in which the coefficients F_n , G_n and H_n can be found in [10]. The interlaminar shear strain γ_{xz} at outer surface ($y=-e$) is shown to be

$$\begin{aligned}
 \gamma_{xz} = \gamma_{zx}(z) = & \frac{G_{xy}}{G_{xz}} \theta \left[\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} g_n (n\pi/c) \frac{\sinh(n\pi(z+f)/cp)}{\sinh(pn\pi f/cp)} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} f_n (pn\pi/f) \frac{\sin(n\pi(z+f)/f)}{\sinh(pn\pi c/f)} \right. \\
 & \left. + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} W_n (-pn\pi/f) \frac{\sin(n\pi(z+f)/f)}{\tanh(pn\pi c/f)} \right] \quad (12)
 \end{aligned}$$

and the in-plane shear strain γ_{xy} at $z=e$ surface can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \gamma_{xy} = \theta[-e + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} V_n \frac{\sinh(-pn\pi y/e)}{\sinh(pn\pi c/f)} (-1)^n (n\pi/e) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} h_n \frac{\sinh(pn\pi(y+c)/e)}{\sinh(pn\pi c/e)} (-1)^n (n\pi/e) \\
 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} g_n \frac{\sin(n\pi(y+c)/c)}{\tanh(n\pi e/cp)} (n\pi/cp)] \quad (13)
 \end{aligned}$$

These two formulas can be used to calculate the shear strains in the tested specimens, or to find the in-situ shear moduli G_{xy} and G_{xz} for an edge cracked laminate.

3. Calculation of Strain Energy Release Rate

For this cracked beam, the only energy release rate G_{III} can be calculated as

$$G_{III} = \frac{T^2}{2} \frac{\partial C}{\partial a} \quad (14)$$

where T is the applied torque and C is the compliance function, which is the reciprocal of $GJ(a)$. When substitute Eqn. (4) into above, the G_{III} is seen to be

$$G_{III} = (GJ)^2 \frac{\partial^2}{2} \frac{\partial}{\partial a} \left(\frac{1}{GJ(a)} \right) = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial (GJ(a))}{\partial a} \theta^2 \quad (15)$$

In this equation the derivative of $GJ(a)$ with respect to a can be obtained from the numerical differentiation of the $GJ(a)$ versus crack size a curve without any difficulty. Some examples will be examined later. This equation can be used in the experimental characterization of the critical energy release rate, provided the critical twisting angle or critical torque is measured.

4. Numerical Examples

The $[\pm 15]_{10S}$, and $[0/90]_{10S}$ laminates with interfacial crack located at the innermost interface are examined. The material used assumes the following properties.

$$E_1 = 138 \text{ GPa}, E_2 = E_3 = 10.0 \text{ GPa}$$

$$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.3, \nu_{23} = 0.45$$

$$G_{12} = G_{13} = 6.9 \text{ GPa}, \quad G_{23} = 3.45 \text{ GPa}$$

and the corresponding G_{xy} and G_{xz} for these three orientations are calculated from Eqn. (1)

$$G_{xy} = 14.12 \text{ GPa}, \quad G_{xz} = 6.47 \text{ GPa} \quad \text{for } [\pm 15]_{10S}$$

$$G_{xy} = 6.90 \text{ GPa}, \quad G_{xz} = 4.60 \text{ GPa} \quad \text{for } [0/90]_{10S}$$

Three kinds of methods are compared. The analytical series solution using the formulas derived above to obtain the GJ and G_{III} . The details of these two finite element methods can be seen in [10]. Fig. 3 is the comparison of G_{III} values at $\theta = 1 \text{ rad/m}$ for $[\pm 15]_{10S}$ and $[0/90]_{10S}$ laminates. It is seen that the analytical series solution can achieve good results when a/d is greater than 10. The thickness of one sublaminar is denoted by d ($d =$ two ply thickness in this case $= 0.254 \text{ mm}$). In Table 1, the energy release rates from each mode are listed. It is obvious for this kind of torsion loading, the fracture is dominated by Mode III, the sum of G_I and G_{II} is less than 0.5% of G_{III} .

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Specimens made from AS4/3501-6 are used in this experiment. Starter cracks are made by embedding 1 mil (0.0254mm) thick teflon films between the plies during the layup. This teflon film is nonstick and high temperature resistant. Typical specimen is shown in Fig. 4. A manually operated torsion machine (see Fig. 4) is used to perform the torsion test. Two LVDTs (linear variable differential transformer) located at different points are attached on the top surface to measure the vertical displacements.

The specimen is loaded under fixed grip condition till the crack propagates. When the crack propagation stops, the specimen is unloaded and x-rayed to find the position of crack tip, i.e. a_1 . This crack length is used in the data reduction or series solution thereafter. A typical T- θ curve is shown in Fig. 5. In the experiment, the T- θ curve is recorded. From this T- θ curve, the T_{cr} and the slope of T/ θ (or in situ GJ) are obtained. From Eqn. (15), the critical energy release rate G_{IIIc} can be calculated as

$$G_{IIIc} = G_{III} \theta_{cr}^2 = G_{III} \left(\frac{T_{cr}}{T_0} \right)^2 \tag{16}$$

in which T_0 is seen to equal to GJ when $\theta = 1 \text{ rad/m}$ and G_{III} is yielded from Eqn (15) when $\theta = 1 \text{ rad/m}$.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Three types of interface crack specimens are tested. The specimens tested here are $[0/90]_{10S}$, $[\pm 15]_{8S}$, $[\pm 15]_{10S}$, and $[\pm 45]_{10S}$ which contains single edge crack located at the innermost interface. The nominal dimension of each specimen is 5.0 cm. wide and 28.0 cm. long. The material used is AS4 3501-6 graphite/epoxy with the following properties,

$$E_1 = 138 \text{ GPa}, \quad E_2 = E_3 = 10.0 \text{ GPa}$$

$$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13} = 0.3, \quad \nu_{23} = 0.48$$

The material shear moduli G_{12} , G_{13} and G_{23} are characterized by the method in [9]. For 0/90 interface, twelve $[0/90]_{10S}$ specimens are tested. Fig. 6 shows the final position of the crack front. Uniform crack fronts are observed. The experimental effective shear moduli are $G_{xy} = 5.7\text{-}6.2 \text{ GPa}$, and $G_{xz} = 4.2 \text{ GPa}$. The G_{IIIc} for $[0/90]_{10S}$ laminate ranges from 740 to 980 J/m^2 , with an average of 825 J/m^2 (see Table 2). For $\pm 15^\circ$ interface cracks, the fractures

happened suddenly, therefore the initial size of the artificial damage is taken as the initial crack size a_1 . The torque drops sharply at certain twisting angle (see Fig. 5). Table 2 summarize the average results of G_{IIC} values for 8 test specimens. The G_{IIC} is around 700 J/m². The average effective shear moduli are $G_{xy}=12.1$ GPa, and $G_{xz}=4.5$ GPa. Several specimens are tested to find the G_{IIC} for $[\pm 45]_{10S}$ laminate. The effective moduli for this orientation are $G_{xy}=35.76$ GPa, and $G_{xz}=4.38$ GPa respectively. The average G_{IIC} value for these tested specimens is 450 J/m². The final crack front can be seen in Fig. 6.

From the test results the G_{IIC} values range from 460 to 825 J/m². A comparison of G_{IIC} values between this study and [1] is shown in Table 2. In [1] the G_{IIC} for $\pm 15^\circ$ interface is 1650 ± 200 J/m² for $[75_4/-75_8//75_4]$ laminate (which is equivalent to the $\pm 15^\circ$ interface in this study), here the G_{IIC} values are half of those, i.e., 695 ± 40 J/m². The difference between these two methods is that for the split cantilever beam specimens used in [1], the mixed mode effect was not judged accurately. The limitation of the testing method proposed here is that the specimen can not be too thin, since for thin laminate under torsional loading, the twisting angle is large and the small deformation theory can not be applied. Another drawback is that for angle ply with orientation angle larger than 45° , the specimens break at the middle portion. Although from the effective modulus theory, the $[\pm \theta]$ laminates will have the same torsion behaviors as the $[(\pm(90 - \theta))]$ laminates.

CONCLUSION

A method for measuring the interlaminar Mode III fracture toughness of composite laminates is proposed. Experimental procedure and analytical series solutions to characterize the G_{IIC} value are discussed. Test results for 0/90, +15/-15 and +45/-45 interlaminar fracture toughness show that the G_{IIC} ranges from 460 to 825 J/m². This torsional fracture theory and testing method can be used to find the Mode III fracture toughness.

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Table 1. Strain energy release rates G (J/m^2) for $[\pm 45]_{105}$ laminate at $\theta=1$ rad/m by local finite element method and analytical series solution.

$a/2b$	G_I FEM	G_{II} FEM	G_{III} FEM	G_{total} FEM	G_{III} Series solution
0.0125	0.079	0.317	183.75	184.14	157.2
0.025	0.004	0.227	290.22	290.45	268.5
0.05	0.009	0.109	427.98	428.03	412.3
0.1	0.011	0.070	535.90	531.70	531.8
0.15	0.011	0.069	571.50	571.58	567.4
0.2	0.012	0.07	584.85	584.93	578.5
0.3	0.081	0.018	584.17	584.27	582.9
0.4	0.081	0.019	583.15	583.25	581.9
0.5	0.080	0.019	578.62	578.72	577.4
0.6	0.079	0.020	564.14	564.24	563.5
0.7	0.075	0.027	522.84	522.94	522.7
0.8	0.060	0.037	410.83	410.93	411.2

$2b=5.08$ cm

Table 2. Comparison of G_{IIIc} (J/m^2) with Donaldson's results [1]

interface type	present	Donaldson
± 15	695 ± 40	1650 ± 200
± 75	N.A.	1650 ± 200
± 45	460 ± 40	780 ± 120
0/90	825 ± 70	N.A.

Figure 1. Torsion of thick laminate.

Figure 2. Cross-section geometry of edge cracked orthotropic bar.

Figure 3. Energy release rates for $[\pm 15]_{10s}$ and $[0/90]_{10s}$ laminates ($\theta = 1 \text{ rad/m}$).

Figure 4. Specimen and torsion machine setup.

Figure 5. T- θ curve of $[\pm 15]_{10s}$ laminate, $2b = 4.94 \text{ cm}$, $2h = 0.54 \text{ cm}$.

Figure 6. Final crack position of $[0/90]_{10s}$, $[\pm 15]_{10s}$ and $[\pm 45]_{10s}$ specimens.